

THE ROLE OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation. This article is about benefits and the main directions of extracurricular activities in teaching process.

Keywords: extracurricular activities, teaching process, cooperative learning groups, main directions of extracurricular activities

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена преимуществам и основным направлениям внеурочной деятельности в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: внеурочная деятельность, учебный процесс, совместные учебные группы, основные направления внеурочной деятельности

Extra – curricular work in foreign languages becomes more and more popular. This work is carried out both in town and village schools. Various books and articles on the subject recently published are a proof of the popularity of this work among foreign language teachers and its importance in attaining the aims and objectives set by the syllabus. However, there are many schools where teachers either do not carry out extra – curricular work of this kind is not obligatory; it is just additional, therefore they may do it only if time permits. These teachers do not realize that their success in foreign language teaching depends to a great extent on what interest they can evoke in their pupils. Cooperative learning groups are typically made up of students or pupils with heterogeneous backgrounds and abilities. By working together to succeed in groups, they learn to appreciate differences in skills, aptitudes, learning styles, personalities, goals, and interest. Cooperative learning also helps learners to reach higher academic achievement levels. The best way to avoid interpersonal problems, whether in pairs or small groups, is to structure the cooperative learning activities so

that the content is challenging and the pace is appropriate. Avoid monotony by planning a balance of whole – class, pair, small group, and individual activities.

Extracurricular activities are an integral part of the entire educational process and contribute to the creative development of students, creating favorable conditions for the formation and development of socio-cultural competence. The standard of basic general education in a foreign language states: "socio-cultural competence - familiarizing students with the culture, traditions and realities of the country of the foreign language being studied...; forming the ability to represent their country, its culture in the conditions of foreign-language intercultural communication."

It is possible to distinguish the main directions of extracurricular activities:

- Formation and development of students' communication skills;
- Expanding the horizons of students in the field of country studies
- Increase motivation for further learning of foreign languages.
- Development of students' research skills.

The unity of these main directions will ensure the harmonious development of the individual in the system of extracurricular work in a foreign language. The principle of the child's activity in the process.

Gaming technology dominates extracurricular activities for a reason. It is this technology that better helps to solve practical, general education and educational tasks. The game meets the interests of the children's team, since most often it does not take much time, is not cumbersome, promotes the use of situational speech patterns, and is successfully combined with the entire system of the educational process. The main thing is to keep in mind the level of language readiness of students, taking into account their age and individual characteristics and the principle of intersubject relations. It is not difficult for a foreign language teacher to follow this principle, since it is the foreign language teacher who is the most widely educated teacher in the school, because no school subject has a connection with as many other subjects as a foreign language. The role of inter-subject relations is very important, since the ultimate goal of the entire educational process of the school is the formation of a fully developed.

During the preparation and conduct of extracurricular activities, the teacher needs to worry together with the children, doubt, look for answers to emerging questions, help solve problems. The teacher should have a good idea of what the children expect from him, because they are the main indicators of our activity.

Extracurricular activities work as stress buster. To be fully involved in the studies can make students feel fatigue. Academic curriculum seems to be very

vast these days, so it becomes really necessary to give some refreshing treatments to students. Such activities keep students happy and being happy itself means keeping depressions and stress at bay. It increase concentration power of the students enhances their academic performance. While learning in schools or colleges most of the time of the students passes while sitting. But the age of students requires more physical activities. Absence of adequate physical activities can lead to a lot of health disorders. Obesity is one of the worst outcomes of it. Involving in such activities improves digestion which ensures good functioning of almost all the body parts by supplying proper nutrients to all the body parts. Students can learn time management with help of these activities. Adjusting study and extracurricular activities can make students wiser in managing their time. They also learn multitasking through it. The team spirit in the students also enhances with these activities. Most extracurricular activities involve teamwork. Thus the students learn how to work in a team.

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